

1 **Effect of traditional and modern culinary processing, bioaccessibility, biosafety**
2 **and bioavailability of eritadenine, a hypocholesterolemic compound from edible**
3 **mushrooms**

4 Diego Morales^{*1}, María Tabernero^{2,3}, Carlota Largo², Gonzalo Polo², Adriana J. Piris¹,
5 Cristina Soler-Rivas¹

6 ¹ Department of Production and Characterization of Novel Foods, Institute of Food Science
7 Research - CIAL (UAM+CSIC), C/ Nicolas Cabrera 9, Campus de Cantoblanco, Universidad
8 Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

9 ²Department of Experimental Surgery, Research Institute Hospital La Paz (IdiPAZ), Paseo de la
10 Castellana 261, 28046 Madrid, Spain

11 ³ Department of Innovation in Precision Nutrition, Imdea-Food Institute, CEI UAM+CSIC,
12 Carretera de Cantoblanco 8. 28049, Madrid, Spain.

13 * Corresponding author: diego.morales@uam.es

14 **Abstract**

15 Eritadenine is a hypocholesterolemic compound that was found in several mushroom
16 species such as *Lentinula edodes*, *Marasmius oreades*, *Amanita caesarea* (1.4, 0.7 and 0.6
17 mg/g dw, respectively). It was synthesized during all developmental stages being present in
18 higher concentrations in the skin of shiitake fruiting bodies. When submitted to traditional
19 cooking, grilling followed by frying were more adequate methodologies than boiling or
20 microwaving to maintain its levels. Modern culinary processes such as texturization (with agar-
21 agar), spherification (with alginate) also interfered with its release. Grilling and gelling using
22 gelatin enhanced eritadenine bioaccessibility in an *in vitro* digestion model. An animal model
23 (where male and female rats were administrated 21 and 10 mg/kg animal/day of eritadenine)
24 indicated that in taking of the compound was safe under those concentrations, it reached the
25 liver and reduced the atherogenic index (TC/HDL) in rat sera. Thus, it might be used to design a
26 functional food.

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Edible mushrooms are consumed worldwide due to their particular flavors and
29 nutritional values. Their consumption is also encouraged because of their health promoting
30 properties *e.g.* their ability to lower cholesterol levels in serum. Therefore, certain mushroom
31 species could be used as starting material to design functional foods. They contain fungal
32 sterols and β -glucans that can impair dietary cholesterol absorption¹ and other molecules that
33 affect the biosynthesis of endogenous cholesterol.^{2,3} They also synthesize other compounds
34 such as eritadenine that can also indirectly influence serum LDL levels.⁴

35 Eritadenine ((2(R),3(R)-dihydroxy-4-(9-adenyl)butanoic acid), also named lentysine or
36 lentynacin, is an adenosine analog derived from the secondary metabolism that was firstly
37 isolated from shiitake mushrooms (*Lentinula edodes*).⁵ Several studies demonstrated that its
38 hypocholesterolemic activity in mice and rats was related to its ability as S-adenosyl-L-
39 homocysteine hydrolase (SAHH) inhibitor. Eritadenine modulated hepatic phospholipid
40 metabolism by decreasing the phosphatidylcholine (PC)/phosphatidylethanolamine (PE) ratio.
41 However, its precise mechanism of action is not yet fully elucidated^{4,6,7} and therefore, certain
42 safety risks might arise if food products are functionalized by adding eritadenine-enriched
43 extracts as hypocholesterolemic ingredients.

44 Another aspect to take into consideration is the fact that edible mushrooms (or those
45 functionalized foods) are not usually consumed raw but they are submitted to culinary
46 treatments before ingestion. These processes, usually involving heat (boiling, grilling, etc.),
47 might modulate the concentrations of the fungal bioactive molecules that are assimilated.^{8,9}
48 Moreover, novel culinary procedures that are nowadays in trend, presenting surprising dishes
49 or food products (gelling, spherification, etc.) to potentiate consumer interest, might influence
50 their levels too since they include food additives in their formulations (hydrocolloids,
51 thickeners, etc.). These additives could directly interact with the bioactive ingredients
52 modifying their bioaccessibility. Later on, the bioactive compounds that survive the culinary

53 treatments might be further modified during mastication, stomach and/or intestinal digestions
54 influencing their absorption levels at the human intestine.¹⁰ However, not many studies have
55 been carried out to evaluate the influence of all these processes on bioactive compounds such
56 as eritadenine.

57 Therefore, a screening through several edible mushrooms was carried out to find an
58 interesting eritadenine source. Different fruiting body tissues and developmental stages were
59 also investigated. Then, shiitake mushrooms were submitted to traditional and modern
60 culinary processings to evaluate their effect on eritadenine stability. Afterwards, the effect of
61 digestion on eritadenine bioaccessibility was studied using an *in vitro* digestion model and its
62 toxicity, bioavailability and hypocholesterolemic effect were evaluated with *in vivo* animal
63 experiments.

64 **2. Materials & Methods**

65 *2.1. Biological material*

66 Mushroom species such as *Lentinula edodes* S. (Berkeley), *Lactarius deliciosus* (Fr.), *Boletus*
67 *edulis* (Bull. Ex Fr.), *Pleurotus ostreatus* (Jacq.Ex Fr.) Kummer, *Agaricus bisporus* L. (Imbach),
68 *Amanita caesarea* (Scop. Ex Fri.) Pers. Ex Schw., *Cantharellus tubaeformis* (Schaeff) Quel,
69 *Ganoderma lucidum* (Curtis) P.Karst., *Lyophyllum shimeji* (Kawam.), *Morchella conica* (Pers.),
70 *Auricularia auricula judae* (Bull. Ex St.Amans) Berck, *Marasmius oreades* (Bolt. Ex Fr.) Fr were
71 purchased in season from the local market in Madrid (Spain). They were lyophilized and
72 ground into fine powder as described by Ramirez-Anguiano *et al.* (2007)¹¹. Dried mushroom
73 powders were stored at -20 °C until further use.

74 Fresh *Lentinula edodes* fruiting bodies were also subjected to traditional cooking
75 treatments (see later) or processed to separate the different tissues with a knife. Then,
76 individual parts were treated as described above.

77 In order to test an eritadenine-enriched preparation as potential functional ingredient for
78 the *in vivo* tests, an extract was obtained by stirring *L. edodes* powder with water (0.5 g/L) for
79 1 min at room temperature. The resulting suspension was centrifuged for 7 min at 7000 rpm at
80 10 °C and the obtained supernatant was immediately frozen and lyophilized. This fraction was
81 an eritadenine-enriched extract containing 3.1 mg /g.

82 2.2. Reagents

83 Solvents such as methanol (HPLC grade) and acetonitrile (HPLC grade) were acquired from
84 Lab-Scan (Gliwice, Poland). Ethanol (HPLC grade), diethyl ether (HPLC grade) and calcium
85 chloride were purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain). Hydrochloric acid (37%),
86 trifluoroacetic acid (99%), sodium hydroxide, pepsin (from porcine gastric mucosa), sodium
87 chloride, Trizma base, maleic acid, pancreatin (from porcine pancreas) and L- α -phosphatidyl
88 choline (lecithin) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain) and D-eritadenine (90%)
89 from SYNCHEM UG & Co. KG (Felsberg, Germany).

90 All additives used for culinary preparations were food grade: gelatin was acquired from
91 Mondelez International (Madrid, Spain) and agar-agar (E406), sodium alginate (E401) and
92 calcium lactate (E327) from Cuisine Innovation (Dijon, France).

93 2.3. Traditional culinary processing

94 *Lentinula edodes* fresh fruiting bodies were cut into slices and cooked (30 g) following four
95 traditional methods: grilling, microwave cooking, frying and boiling. These treatments were
96 carried out as described by Soler-Rivas *et al.* (2009)⁹ in quadruplicate and the resulting cooked
97 mushrooms were directly subjected to an *in vitro* digestion model or freeze-dried, ground and
98 stored at -20°C until further analysis.

99 2.4. Modern culinary processing

100 Lyophilized shiitake fruiting bodies were subjected to modern culinary processes used on
101 molecular gastronomy such as thickening (usually called 'texturization'), gelling and
102 'spherification'.

103 Powdered shiitake mushrooms (500 mg) were mixed with 50 mL water and 1 g agar-agar
104 (as a thickener) and homogenized with a culinary blender (Minipimer 3MR320 Braun,
105 Aschaffenburg, Germany). Afterwards, the mixture was heated up to 100 °C and maintained
106 for 1 min. Then, an aliquot was collected with a 60 mL syringe and injected into a silicone tube
107 (77 cm length and 0.5 cm diameter). The filled tube was partially folded, making loops, and
108 submerged in an ice bath to cool down. The semi-solidified (texturized) gel obtained was
109 extracted from the silicone tube by forcing air inside with another syringe. Then, the texturized
110 shiitake powder resembled semi-transparent spaghetti with a mushroom taste.

111 Powder from the same shiitake batch (500 mg) was added to a previously hydrated gelatin
112 solution obtained by dissolving a gelatin film (1 g) in cold water (50 mL) for 3 min. Then, the
113 mixture was stirred at 75 °C for 2 min. Afterwards, homogenate was poured into a round mold
114 and stored at 4 °C for 2 h allowing gel formation.

115 'Spherification' was carried out by mixing the shiitake powder (500 mg) and sodium
116 alginate (400 mg) with 50 mL water and homogenizing them with a blender until a slightly
117 viscose solution was obtained. The mixture was kept 5 min at room temperature to eliminate
118 bubbles. Then, it was introduced into a 60 mL syringe and slowly dropped on a calcium lactate
119 solution (44 mM). The surface of the liquid drops polymerized when placed in contact with
120 Ca²⁺, yielding jelly spheres. Spheres were left for approx. 3 min, transferred to a water bath to
121 remove calcium excess, taken out with a perforated spoon and plated.

122 Each culinary process was carried out 4 times. The resulting preparations were directly
123 subjected to an *in vitro* digestion model or freeze-dried, ground and stored at -20°C until
124 further analysis.

125 *2.5. In vitro digestion model*

126 Fresh shiitake fruiting bodies, as well as the food preparations resulting from the
127 traditional and modern culinary processes, were digested following the procedure described
128 by Gil-Ramirez *et al.* (2014)¹ with modifications. Samples (15 g of traditional culinary processed
129 shiitake or the modern preparations including 500 mg shiitake powder) were masticated by a
130 volunteer for approx. 2 min and spat into a beaker. Milli-Q water was acidified with 6 M HCl
131 (adjusting the pH to 2.0) and added (54 mL) to the masticated samples. The mixture was
132 transferred to a thermostatic vessel at 37 °C with mild stirring and pepsin (275 mg) was also
133 incorporated. Then, it was incubated for 1 h and stirred in a titrator device (Titrino plus,
134 Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland) simulating gastric digestion. Afterwards, intestinal digestion
135 was initiated by adding 5 mM CaCl₂ and 150 mM NaCl and adjusting the pH to 6.0 by adding
136 0.5 M NaOH. Then, a pancreatic solution (6 mL) containing 20 mg pancreatin, 633 mg bile
137 extract and 228 mg lecithin (in 50 mM Trizma-maleate buffer pH 7.5) was added and the pH
138 was adjusted to 7.5 and maintained for 2 h using a viscotrode (Metrohm, Herisau, Switzerland)
139 placed in the titrator device. The stirring level and temperature were the same than used in
140 the gastric digestion simulation.

141 After the digestion process, digested samples were heated in a water bath at 80 °C for 10
142 min to inactivate digestive enzymes (eritadenine was resistant to this thermal treatment as
143 indicated elsewhere^{12,13}) and then subjected to centrifugation (7000 rpm 15 min) to separate
144 the supernatant that was considered as the bioaccessible fraction.

145 Eritadenine bioaccessibility was estimated to be the ratio (%) between the amount of
146 eritadenine in the bioaccessible fraction and that in the sample before the digestion process.

147 *2.6. Animals and diets*

148 Sprague Dawley adult (5 weeks old) male and female rats ($n = 24$) were purchased from
149 Charles River (San Cugat del Valles, Barcelona, Spain) and housed, separated by sex, in groups

150 of four animals per cage. Animals were maintained under controlled conditions of
151 temperature, humidity and light (24 ± 2 °C, 40–60% humidity, 12 h:12 h light/ dark cycle) and
152 had free access to water and food (commercial rodent maintenance diet A04; Scientific
153 Animals Food & Engineering, Augy, France). After an adaptation period (6 days) animals were
154 weighed and randomly divided into three groups per sex: control group (C) that remained with
155 the standard diet, another group that was fed with a low eritadenine dose (10 mg per kg
156 animal per day) (LE) and the third group was fed a higher dose (HE) (21 mg per kg animal per
157 day). Diets were prepared mixing A04 chow with the corresponding amount of the
158 eritadenine-enriched extract necessary to obtain the indicated eritadenine concentration per
159 group. The nutrient composition of each diet is summarized in **Table 1**. Animals were
160 maintained on this diet for 5 weeks with daily evaluation of behavioral (posture and activity)
161 and physiological (fur and mucosa status, hydration and the presence of secretions and
162 wounds) parameters were scaled by trained staff and weekly monitoring of weight gain. Feces
163 were collected at the beginning and at the end of the experimental period and maintained at
164 -20 °C until further use.

165 The protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of La Paz
166 University Hospital (Madrid, Spain) and procedures were performed in accordance with the EU
167 Directive 2010/63/EU and the Spanish law RD 53/2013 regarding the protection of
168 experimental animals.

169 *2.7. Biosafety and bioavailability studies*

170 Following the experimental feeding period (5 weeks), overnight-fasted rats were
171 euthanized by intracardiac exsanguination under anesthesia with 1.5% isoflurane. Plasma was
172 separated out by centrifugation (10 min at 5000 rpm) using sterile tubes pre-treated with
173 EDTA. The supernatant collected was stored at -20 °C until analysis. Plasma levels of total
174 cholesterol (TC), HDL cholesterol, triglycerides, glucose and circulating renal and liver damage

175 biomarkers (creatinine, uric acid, bilirubin, alanine transaminase (ALT), aspartate transaminase
176 (AST)) were measured in duplicate for each sample using a Covas C311 Autoanalyzer (Roche,
177 Basel, Switzerland) specifically calibrated for rodent samples. All enzymatic colorimetric kits
178 and internal quality controls were supplied by Roche (Basel, Switzerland).

179 Livers, spleen, kidneys and testis or ovaries were collected, weighed and washed in ice-
180 cold PBS. Samples were processed for each tissue, keeping a fraction fixed in 10% neutral
181 buffered formalin for 24 hours and the other part was immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen
182 and storage at -80 °C until analysis. Fixed samples were embedded in paraffin for further
183 analysis by immunohistochemistry. Afterwards, frozen liver samples were subjected to
184 homogenization to detect eritadenine (see later).

185 2.8. Eritadenine determination by HPLC-DAD

186 Eritadenine was extracted from samples and quantified following two different methods.
187 One of them (method 1) was based on the procedure of Enman *et al.* (2007)¹⁴ with slight
188 modifications. In this case, samples (1 g) were mixed with 20 mL of 80% methanol (v/v) and
189 stirred in the dark for 3 h. Then, the mixture was filtered through a 14–18 µm pore size paper
190 filter (GE Healthcare Europe GmbH 1240, Barcelona, Spain) and methanol was removed on a
191 rotary vacuum evaporator (60 °C), keeping the sample protected from light. Afterwards, the
192 dried extract was mixed with 10 mL Milli-Q water, washed 3 times with diethyl ether, mixed
193 with 40 mL ethanol (4:1, v/v) and kept overnight at -20 °C. Finally, the sample was filtered
194 through filter paper, and ethanol was removed using the rotary vacuum evaporator and water
195 using a freeze-dryer. The resulting eritadenine extract was stored at -20 °C until further use.

196 The second extraction method (method 2) followed the Afrin *et al.* (2016)¹⁵ procedure.
197 Briefly, samples (1 g) were mixed with 10 mL of 60% ethanol (v/v) and stirred for 2 min. The
198 mixture was subjected to centrifugation (7000 rpm, 15 min) in a Heraus Multifuge 3SR+
199 centrifuge (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Madrid, Spain) and the supernatant was carefully

200 collected. The pellet was extracted twice and supernatants were pooled together, filtered and
201 dried as explained in method 1.

202 Eritadenine was extracted from livers by homogenizing the organs with an IKA Werke T8
203 Ultra Turrax (Ika Works Inc., Staufen, Germany) at maximum power. Resulting homogenates
204 were mixed with 10 mL of 60% ethanol (v/v) and stirred for 2 min, following method 2.

205 The identification and quantification of eritadenine were carried out using an HPLC system
206 (Pro-Star 330, Varian, Madrid, Spain) equipped with a PDA detector (Pro-Star 363 module,
207 Varian, Madrid, Spain). Samples were dissolved in the mobile phase (5 mg/mL), injected (10
208 μ L) into a C18 Spherisorb ODS2 analytical column (4 x 250 mm, 5 μ m, Waters, Missisagua,
209 Ontario, Canada) and developed at 0.5 mL/min with water : acetonitrile (98:2, 1% v/v TFA).
210 Eritadenine was quantified at 260 nm using a commercial standard (0.004 – 0.25 mg/mL). The
211 compound eluted after 10.5 min and showed the characteristic eritadenine UV-spectrum.

212 2.9. Statistical analysis

213 Differences were evaluated at 95 % confidence level ($P \leq 0.05$) using one-way analysis of
214 variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's Multiple Comparison test. Statistical analysis was
215 performed using SPSS V.13.0 software (SPSS Institute Inc., Cary, NC) and GraphPad Prism
216 version 5.01 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA).

217 3. Results and Discussion

218 3.1. Determination of eritadenine in several edible mushrooms

219 Eritadenine was firstly isolated from *Lentinula edodes*⁵ but not many other species were
220 investigated to study whether they might contain interesting concentrations. Therefore,
221 before selecting shiitake as a source of the metabolite, a preliminary screening of a few other
222 related mushroom species was carried out. Eritadenine was extracted from selected
223 mushrooms following two already described methods because they both claimed to be specific

224 for eritadenine determination but their procedures were different.^{14,15} Results indicated that
225 indeed *L. edodes* was the mushroom with higher eritadenine concentrations but a few others
226 species contained it too although in lower concentrations (Figure 1a). Extraction of eritadenine
227 using method 1 yielded slightly lower levels of this metabolite than extraction using method 2
228 and this difference seemed to occur similarly within all the analyzed species. Apparently, the
229 longer incubation times utilized in method 1 did not increase extraction yield.

230 *Lentinula edodes* contained 1.0 or 1.4 mg/g (depending on the method utilized), levels that
231 were lower than those in some publications^{14,15} but higher than others.¹⁶ However, the fact
232 that both methods indicated similar concentrations suggested that differences with respect to
233 the other publications might be because of different cultivation conditions, processing,
234 mushroom strains, etc. Other mushroom species such as *Marasmius oreades*, belonging to the
235 same family as *L. edodes* (Marasmiaceae), showed 0.7 mg/g eritadenine (according to method
236 2), only half the shiitake levels, suggesting that closely related species might also be used to
237 synthesize significant amounts of this compound. Eritadenine was also found in other
238 mushrooms belonging to the same order as *L. edodes* (Agaricales) such as *Amanita caesarea*
239 (0.6 mg/g), *Lyophyllum shimeji*, *Agaricus bisporus* and *Pleurotus ostreatus* (approx. 0.2 mg/g).
240 But other mushrooms not so closely related, such as *Boletus edulis*, *Morchella conica* and
241 *Lactarius deliciosus* also contained similar eritadenine concentrations (0.2 mg/g). Therefore,
242 the presence of the compound in higher concentrations might be only attributed to the
243 *Lentinula* genus.

244 3.2. Production of eritadenine by shiitake fruiting bodies

245 A more detailed study about the eritadenine biosynthesis was carried out by determining
246 its production within different fruiting bodies tissues and during their development. The
247 results indicated that differences between tissues were more pronounced when using method
248 2 than 1. Within the cap, eritadenine was present in higher concentrations in the epidermis

249 than in the dermis or gills (Figure 1b). The role of this compound in the mushroom metabolism
250 has still not been elucidated although some studies suggested its involvement in defense (as
251 antibiotic nucleoside) like many other derivatives from the secondary metabolism.^{17,18} If this
252 was the case, it seemed adequate to concentrate the compound in the tissue with direct
253 contact with the environment. The stipe also contained the compound but in lower
254 concentration being in concordance with previous observations indicated by Saito *et al.*
255 (1975)¹⁶ where lower levels of eritadenine were found in all the stipes compared to the caps of
256 several shiitake strains.

257 Moreover, when eritadenine biosynthesis was studied during the development of the
258 fruiting bodies, the results indicated that the metabolite was produced in similar
259 concentrations during their complete growth since no differences were found within
260 developmental stages (Table 2). Although mature mushrooms showed slightly higher
261 eritadenine contents (using method 2) differences with earlier stages were not statistically
262 significant. Therefore, since method 2 was an easier procedure and differences between
263 samples were broader than method 1, method 2 was selected for further eritadenine
264 quantifications.

265 3.3. Effect of traditional culinary treatments in eritadenine stability and bioaccessibility

266 In order to investigate whether eritadenine might be assimilated by shiitake consumers,
267 the effect of traditional culinary treatments applied to the mushroom before its consumption
268 was evaluated. Furthermore, processed fruiting bodies were submitted to an *in vitro* digestion
269 model mimicking human digestion to determine eritadenine concentrations in the bioaccessible
270 fraction.

271 The dry heat irradiated during grilling did not significantly affected eritadenine levels
272 compared to raw mushrooms (Figure 2a). Apparently, eritadenine was heat stable as also
273 indicated by previous studies.^{12,13} However, when other cooking treatments involving water as

274 heat transmitter medium were used, such as microwave or boiling, eritadenine content was
275 reduced. Temperatures in these processes were milder than grilling; therefore, its losses might
276 be due to lixiviation into the aqueous medium because of its hydrophilic nature. But, when a
277 lipid medium was utilized for frying, a decrease in eritadenine content was also noticed.
278 Perhaps the deeper penetration of the oil through the mushroom tissues brought the higher
279 reached temperature (160 °C) to more internal parts of the mushroom entering more in direct
280 contact with the molecule. When dry heat is used, although the irradiated temperature is
281 higher than frying (200 °C), only the skin and first outer layers of tissue receive such
282 irradiation. The inner parts are cooked by their own water content (meaning maximum 100 °C)
283 because of the cooling effect of water evaporation and because biological materials show very
284 low thermic conductivities. The dry heat reaching the skin induced a Maillard crust that might
285 impair the leaching out of constitutive water containing the eritadenine.

286 After the culinary treatments, shiitake mushrooms were treated with digestive enzymes at
287 specific pH values that simulate mastication and stomach and intestinal digestion. The
288 resulting water-soluble digestates were considered as the fraction that might reach the
289 enterocyte layer in the intestine where absorption takes place. The results indicated that,
290 although grilled mushrooms showed similar eritadenine values than raw mushrooms after the
291 digestion, the compound from the grilled mushrooms was more bioaccessible since almost
292 69.3% of the compound was found in the bioaccessible fraction, while if raw mushrooms were
293 digested only 26.9% was noticed (Figure 2a). Apparently, the heat treatment partially
294 disintegrated the structural fibers and hyphae facilitating its release into the bioaccessible
295 phase. It could be similar to the effect of the glucanases and chitinases utilized by Enman *et al.*
296 (2007)¹⁴ to extract higher eritadenine concentrations from shiitake tissues.

297 Moreover, if cooking and digestion are considered, the high temperatures reached during
298 frying were not so detrimental because although part of the eritadenine was lost during the

299 process, it facilitated the release of the remaining levels into the bioaccessible fraction (59.1%)
300 reaching levels higher than the other culinary treatments involving water (30.8% bioaccessibility
301 after microwave cooking and 35.4% after boiling). The further degradation in the latter
302 treatments could be due to the fact that once the eritadenine is leached in the medium after
303 cooking, it might be more accessible to digestive enzymes. Nevertheless, the eritadenine levels
304 that, in principle, still might reach the enterocytes are similar to those of raw mushrooms.

305 *3.4. Effect of modern culinary treatments in eritadenine stability and bioaccessibility*

306 The effect of novel culinary procedures such as thickening (called 'texturization' by chefs),
307 spherification and gelatinization on the eritadenine concentrations was also tested. The
308 eritadenine content of gelatinized mushroom powder was similar to the non-treated powder
309 (raw), suggesting that the mild treatment required to prepare this gel did not negatively
310 influenced its levels (Figure 2b). However, when the mushroom powder was subjected to
311 texturization or spherification, a large reduction of eritadenine was noticed. During
312 texturization high temperatures were used to dissolve the agar-agar but spherification was
313 carried out at room temperature; therefore, degradation by heat could not be the reason for
314 their lower eritadenine content. Moreover, the above results indicated that the compound
315 resisted temperatures higher than 100 °C. Thus, the other possibility might be that, during the
316 culinary procedure, eritadenine could be scavenged by the polysaccharides used to elaborate
317 the dishes (alginate and agar-agar) forming complexes that hindered eritadenine release with
318 the extraction method utilized (method 2). The fact that [Emman *et al.* \(2007\) \[12\]](#) suggested to
319 use glucanases and chitinases for its extraction might also support this possibility, particularly
320 because if the gel was generated using proteins such as gelatin, an easy release of the
321 compound was noticed.

322 The eritadenine of the shiitake gels generated using proteins or agar-agar was protected
323 from digestive enzymes as its levels remained the same after digestion (Figure 2b). However,

324 when spherification was carried out only 40.1% of the spherified eritadenine was bioaccessible;
325 perhaps, the bonds between alginate and eritadenine were stronger than in the other two gels
326 and were resistant to digestion. Nevertheless, its bioaccessible levels were similar to raw
327 mushroom powder with no culinary treatment.

328 *3.5. Biosafety of diets containing eritadenine*

329 The animal intervention was performed with male and female rats administered two
330 different eritadenine doses (high (HE) and low (LE)) and a control group (C) without the
331 metabolite. The LE group received the same eritadenine concentration as previous animal
332 studies since it was indicated as an effective dose with hypocholesterolemic effect in mice.⁷
333 The HE group received double the amount to test not only its effectiveness but also its
334 biosafety. However, the compound was administered as a food-grade eritadenine-enriched
335 extract to study its potential as a functional ingredient to formulate novel foods and determine
336 whether the rest of the compounds included in the preparation interfered with or enhanced
337 its bioavailability. During the whole intervention, the appearance, behavior and physiology of
338 animals remained stable. Animal weight gain was recorded during the whole intervention and
339 no differences were observed between groups (Figure 3). Independently of the studied sex,
340 tissues collected and evaluated did not show damages or differences in weight compared with
341 the control group (Figure 4). Based on those results, further immunohistochemical analyses
342 were not performed. Plasma samples were determined to evaluate circulating lipid profile,
343 glucose and biomarkers related to renal and liver function (Table 3). All circulating biomarkers
344 determined were not different from those reported in the control group, except for AST
345 concentrations (aspartate transaminase) that were significantly lower in the LE group than that
346 in the C group (males and females) and total cholesterol that was significantly lower in the LE
347 group than in the C group but only in males. But a slight increase of uric acid levels was also
348 noticed with increasing extract administration.

349 3.6 Bioavailability and hypocholesterolemic properties of eritadenine

350 Eritadenine could be detected in livers using the previously described chromatographic
351 method (Figure 5). Control rats did not show the eritadenine peak with R.T. 10.5 min while a
352 compound with spectrum compatible with eritadenine could be detected in some of the livers
353 treated with both doses. In 3 livers from the male rats treated with high eritadenine
354 concentration, the molecule was present within 262.9 to 107.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fw while only 2 of those
355 treated with lower dose showed eritadenine (41.9 and 101.3 $\mu\text{g/g}$). In the liver from female
356 rats, concentrations were slightly lower, being detected only in 2 of the livers from rats
357 administrated with the higher dose (77.4 and 89.6 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and only 1 of the livers administrated
358 with the lower dose (67.5 $\mu\text{g/g}$).

359 Moreover, an approx. 24% lowering of the atherogenic index TC/HDL was noticed with the
360 lower eritadenine concentration tested compared to the controls (Table 3). This reduction was
361 slightly less pronounced than the approx. 29% noticed in mice for the same eritadenine
362 concentration.⁷ Differences could be due to the different animal/physiological conditions (mice
363 were hypercholesterolemic) or because eritadenine was administered as a standard
364 compound in the previous study. The latter case would indicate that the use of a fungal extract
365 partially impaired the eritadenine bioavailability. Nevertheless, in the same study, *L. edodes*
366 was also directly administered and effective lowering of cholesterol levels was reached (5 and
367 10% *L. edodes* administration induced, respectively, 10 and 39 % TC/HDL reduction). Similar
368 values were obtained in this study for male rats (24 and 31 % reduction was noticed for the
369 tested doses, administered as 4.8 and 10 % of the diet). Unfortunately, the previous study did
370 not determine the precise eritadenine concentration in the mushroom, nor indicated the
371 animal sex, so no further comparison could be made.

372 4. Conclusion

373 Besides *Lentinula edodes*, eritadenine was found in significant amounts in other
374 mushrooms such as *Marasmius oreades* and *Amanita caesarea*. It was synthesized during the
375 complete fruiting body growth, being present in higher concentrations in the skin. The
376 molecule showed certain thermal stability since losses due to common culinary treatments
377 were lower than 35% in all cases. Grilling was recommended more than other methods *e.g.*
378 boiling or microwaving not only to maintain high eritadenine concentrations but because it
379 also enhanced its bioaccessibility, probably by facilitating extraction of the compound from the
380 food matrix or protecting it from digestive enzymes. Moreover, a careful selection of the food
381 additives utilized in molecular gastronomy should be made since the use of hydrocolloids such
382 as alginates or agar-agar might scavenge the compound impairing its bioaccessibility.
383 Administration of eritadenine to rats, supplemented as a bioactive ingredient in a normal diet,
384 did not induce damage to any organ or metabolic disorder when added at concentrations up
385 to 21 mg per kg animal per day for 35 days; therefore, it could be considered as safe. It was
386 detected in liver, suggesting that it was bioavailable and could reach that tissue. The extract
387 reduced TC/HDL index in serum of male/female rats although it slightly increased uric acid
388 levels. Therefore, functionalization of foods including an eritadenine-enriched extract obtained
389 from shiitake mushrooms to design a hypocholesterolemic product could be possible since
390 apparently it resists culinary processing, it was not toxic, and it was absorbed and was effective
391 at lowering cholesterol in rats. However, clinical trials are still necessary to confirm these
392 effects in humans.

393 **Conflicts of interest**

394 There are no conflicts to declare.

395 **Acknowledgements**

396 This research was supported by national R+ D program from the Spanish Ministry of
397 Science and Innovation (project AGL2014-56211-R) and the regional program from the
398 Community of Madrid, Spain (S2013/ABI-2728).

399 Marta Moreno-Ortega and Marina Cambor-Murube are acknowledged for their
400 technical assistance.

401 **Abbreviations**

402 SAHH (S-adenosyl-L-homocysteine hydrolase); PC (phosphatidyl choline); PE
403 (phosphatidyl ethanolamine); LE (low eritadenine dose); HE (high eritadenine dose), ALT
404 (alanine transaminase), AST (aspartate transaminase), LDL (low-density lipoprotein), HDL (high-
405 density lipoprotein), TC (total cholesterol).

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Table 1: Nutritional composition of diets. Rodent standard diet (A04) supplemented with high and low doses of the eritadenine-enriched extract containing 3.1 mg/g eritadenine. Results are expressed as g/100 g in dry base.

	<i>High Dose</i>	<i>Low Dose</i>	<i>Control</i>
Carbohydrates	54	57	60
Protein	14.4	15.3	16
Lipids	2.7	2.9	3
Dietary fibre	3.6	3.8	4
Eritadenine-enriched extract	10	4.8	----

Table 2: Eritadenine content (mg/g dry weight) in different developmental stages of *Lentinula edodes* fruiting bodies. No statistical significant differences were found.

Developmental stage	Eritadenine content (mg/g)	
	Method 1	Method 2
Immature	1.23±0.01	1.46±0.03
Intermediate	1.01±0.09	1.44±0.13
Mature	1.23±0.01	1.71±0.02

Table 3: Plasma lipid profile, glucose concentrations and circulating liver and renal damage biomarkers (all values are expressed in mg/dL except for ALT and AST that are IU/L). Statistical significant differences were indicated with the symbol (*).

	Males			Females		
	High dose	Low dose	Control	High dose	Low dose	Control
Total cholesterol (TC)	60.75±2.75	52.75±17.06 *	80.00±11.50	71.50±11.73	77.25±9.5	87.00±2.16
HDL-cholesterol	23.25±1.63	18.13±5.45	20.95±2.05	21.77±3.03	23.45±3.14	20.20±1.66
TC/HDL	2.62±0.09	2.89±0.10	3.80±0.25*	3.27±0.12	3.30±0.05	4.33±0.35*
Triglycerides	100.00±33.46	71.50±10.50	109.50±19.02	70.75±28.25	86.50±19.82	103.00±30.74
Glucose	105.50±14.15	85.25±3.30	78.50±16.38	84.25±9.54	101.00±14.49	87.00±9.31
Creatinine	0.29 ±0.01	0.33±0.06	0.33±0.06	0.31±0.02	0.31±0.03	0.35±0.04
Uric acid	53.75±9.61	41.75±2.22	43.00±5.72	51.25±6.19	47.00±4.55	43.25±3.59
Bilirubin	0.05±0.02	0.07±0.03	0.04±0.03	0.02±0.02	0.05±0.04	0.02±0.01
ALT	38.50 ±8.19	34.25±2.63	33.00±4.32	43.50±15.8	34.50±9.75	32.75±9.39
AST	98.25 ±9.74	95.00±12.68*	129.00±14.73	98.50±7.23	86.25±11.15*	119.75±16.88

Figure captions:

Figure 1: Eritadenine content (mg/g dry weight) in a) several mushroom species and in b) different fruiting body tissues from *Lentinula edodes* determined according to two different methods. Different letters (a-d) denote significant statistical differences between species for the same method ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 2: Eritadenine content (mg/g dry weight) in *Lentinula edodes* submitted to different a) traditional and b) modern culinary treatments and after an *in vitro* digestion model. Different letters (a-b) denote significant statistical differences between culinary treatments and (A-B) between the same culinary treatment and after *in vitro* digestion ($P \leq 0.05$).

Figure 3: Body weight gain during eritadenine supplementation. a) Male and b) female animals supplemented with high dose (■) (0.021 mg/g animal /day) or low dose (□) (0.01 mg/g animal /day) of eritadenine and control group (○). No statistical significant differences were observed between groups.

Figure 4: Organ weight after eritadenine supplementation. Total weight of spleen, liver, kidney and testis/ovary of a) male and b) female animals supplemented with high dose (black bars, 0.021 mg/g animal /day) or low dose (grey bars 0.01 mg/g animal /day) of eritadenine and control group (white bars). No statistical significant differences were observed between supplemented groups.

Figure 5: Chromatograms of liver homogenates obtained from rats supplemented with none (red line) or high (green line) eritadenine dose and an eritadenine standard (black line).

Figure 1:

a)

b)

Figure 2:

a)

b)

Figure 3:

a)

b)

Figure 4:

a)

b)

Figure 5:

